

**THE MAIN ECONOMIC-ECOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF
THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN****Barnokulova Marjona Otabek kizi**

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E-mail: barnoqulovamarjona@gmail.com<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19186934>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 14th March 2026Accepted: 16th March 2026Online: 19th March 2026**KEYWORDS**

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ABSTRACT

The interaction between environmental conditions and human well-being represents a complex and multidimensional process influenced by a wide range of factors. Environmental determinants include social, economic, biological, chemical, physical, and natural-climatic components, each of which plays a significant role in shaping public health and overall quality of life. Understanding the effects of these factors requires comprehensive scientific analysis that examines the causal relationships between environmental changes and human well-being.

Uzbekistan's increasing population and urbanization require a more sustainable use of natural resources and an end to unsustainable consumption and production patterns. The country is particularly vulnerable to the consequences of climate change, and therefore, it is essential to decarbonize its industrial, agricultural, and transport sectors while adapting to new realities.[1] Uzbekistan has one of the world's highest energy intensities, meaning the cost of converting energy into GDP is relatively high. Inefficient energy use costs the country around 4.5 percent of its GDP annually. With 80 percent of its water coming from outside the country, Uzbekistan is vulnerable to water shortages, worsened by climate change. Environmental concerns include land degradation, soil salinization, reduced water quality, wind and water erosion, and decreased productivity of arable land. The poorest segments of the population, who rely on subsistence agriculture in arid regions, are particularly vulnerable to extreme weather events and prolonged droughts associated with the changing climate. The disappearance of the Aral Sea serves as a reminder of the importance of sustainable water management and resource use. The Government of Uzbekistan has been making efforts to balance economic growth with environmental protection, recognizing the need to meet present needs without compromising future opportunities. With its rapid economic development in recent years, Uzbekistan aims to effectively protect and sustainably manage its environment for the benefit of future generations.[2]

The report provides an overview of environmental trends in the context of socio-economic drivers and pressures. Uzbekistan is undergoing major development with considerable population and economic growth. The development progress leads to improvement in employment, income, production, and consumption; it also relies on natural resources, especially water and land. At the same time, this development trajectory is impacting the environment by emitting pollutants, using natural habitat for industrial and agricultural production, and impacting habitat and biodiversity.[3] To explore these linkages between development and the environment, this report uses the DPSIR framework to connect major

drivers and pressures of socio-economic development to the status of the environment. This report summarizes the trends across the major environmental components such as air, water, land, soil, and biodiversity. It also looks at the impacts of climate change, the challenges of Aral Sea degradation, and waste generation. An environmental performance review conducted in 2020 confirmed the main achievements in the environmental sphere in 2009–2019. In addition, a number of key priority future directions were presented (EPR, Uzbekistan, 3rd Review, 2020).[4]

Currently, however, interagency collaboration on the issue of monitoring the implementation of the recommendations proposed in that document has not been established. In light of this, it is advisable to establish a system of monitoring of implementation of these recommendations. In addition, numerous studies of the connection between the environment and health carried out both in Uzbekistan and abroad, show that environmental pollution has a significant adverse effect on the health of the population. The report also outlines examples of major responses to indicate current efforts and inspire future actions. Balancing environmental, social, and economic development aspects is the primary challenge in protecting Uzbekistan's environment and public health. The well-being of the population in terms of environmental, sanitary, and epidemiological conditions is fundamental for citizens to exercise their constitutional rights to health and a clean environment. This requires understanding the impact of a polluted environment on health and well-being. The priority directions of state policy in the field of environmental protection, target indicators, and the Roadmap for the implementation of measures in 2019–2021 and subsequent years are determined within the framework of the Concept of environmental protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, approved by Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Approval of the Concept of Environmental Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, 30 October. As provided for in the approved document, the implementation of the Concept is carried out through the adoption of 3-year roadmaps.[5]

The analysis of climate change shows that the largest impacts will be on agriculture, both through the direct effects of higher temperature and changes in precipitation on yields and because of lower productivity of workers and damages to ecosystems. A study by the International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI) accounted for climate change impacts by shifting production from one crop to another according to which crop is favored by the changes in temperature.

Drinking water quality is a serious problem, especially in the western province of Karakalpakstan, where water is not properly distributed and sources are subject to various types of surface and underground pollution. Inadequate wastewater treatment contributes to Uzbekistan's water pollution problem: only 40 percent of the population is served by sewerage systems. About 15,000 hectares of pasture are lost annually to salt and dust. Soil contamination is highest in agricultural areas, which have been subjected to annual overdoses of fertilizers and pesticides. Uncontrolled logging has endangered the few remaining forest stands. Most industrial cities and settlements are located in zones characterized by low atmospheric dispersion capacity, especially for low and cold emissions. Climatic conditions of Uzbekistan are characterized by weak winds, surface temperature inversion, air stagnation. Fogs are rare here and the amount of precipitation that washes impurities out of the

atmosphere is low. High intensity of solar radiation contributes to photochemical reactions in the polluted atmosphere, which result in formation of various substances, in particular ozone, often more toxic than the primary ones coming directly from pollution sources. Such cities include Tashkent and located in the region Olmaliq, Angren, Okhangaron, Bekabad, Chirchik; enterprises of Andijan and Fergana regions are located in the zone of very high potential atmospheric pollution. High levels of heavy metals such as lead, nickel, zinc, copper, mercury and manganese were found in the atmosphere in Navai of Uzbekistan, mainly as a result of fossil fuel combustion, waste and ferrous and non-ferrous metallurgy. Particularly high concentrations of heavy metals were registered in the Tashkent region and in the southern part of Uzbekistan near the Olmaliq metallurgical plant. Particularly noteworthy is atmospheric pollution in the Saryassi and Denaussi districts of Surkhandarya province, where the air content of hydrogen fluoride, fluorides, sulfur compounds, nitrogen, and carbon determine the emissions of the Tajik aluminum plant, which uses raw materials with elevated fluoride content. As a result, in recent years, nut groves, orchards and vineyards in Saryassia district have died, and 75 families - more than three hundred people - have moved to live in other districts. Increased fluorine content in the air affects the health of the population, the yield of cotton (despite the sanitary protection zone of the plant of 2.5 km). The current situation forced to reduce the plant's capacity by 1/4.

Thus, the country's environmental problems are largely the result of misuse and mismanagement of natural resources, driven by economic and other priorities. For the preservation of the natural environment and the solution of environmental problems, the level of ecological culture of the whole society plays an important role. In order to form and develop environmental culture among the population, it is necessary to create a special methodology of environmental education, on the basis of which and with the help of which people could control their actions and actively form environmental culture. This study emphasizes the importance of integrated research approaches that involve risk assessment, evaluation of population vulnerability, analysis of adaptive capacity, and the development of effective intervention strategies under different environmental scenarios. Such approaches contribute to improving environmental management, strengthening sustainable development policies, and ensuring the protection of human health in the context of global environmental changes.

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